

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Deliverable 6.2

Work package: **WP6**

Dissemination level: **PU**

Lead partner: **ITHACA S.r.l.**

Authors: **Fissore V., Dequal L., Pignocchino G., Monteforte F.**

Due date: **30 / 04 / 2023**

Submission date: **11 / 05 / 2023**

The OVERWATCH project has received funding from the Horizon Europe call “HORIZON-EUSPA-2021”, topic HORIZON-EUSPA-2021-SPACE-02-52, under agreement No. 101082320

Deliverable	Data Management Plan
Deliverable No.	D6.2
Work Package	6
Dissemination Level	PU
Nature ¹	R
Author(s)	Fissore V. (ITHACA)
Co-Author(s)	Dequal L., Pignocchino G., Monteforte F. (ITHACA)
Date	31/05/2023
Status	Second issue
Version	1.1

Deliverable abstract	The Data Management Plan defines how the different types of data will be managed within the 6 WPs of the OVERWATCH project.
----------------------	---

Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily represent the opinion of the European Union. Neither the EUSPA nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

¹ Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report, **P** = Prototype, **D** = Demonstrator, **O** = Other

Table of Content

Document revision history	4
List of authors, contributors and reviewers	4
Abbreviations	4
Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction to OVERWATCH project	6
2. OVERWATCH Consortium	6
3. Aims of the Deliverable	7
4. OVERWATCH Data Summary	7
4.1. WP 1	8
4.2. WP 2 – Wp3 – WP 4	8
4.3. WP 5	11
4.4. WP 6	12
5. FAIR Data	13
5.1 Making Data Findable	14
5.2 Making Data Accessible	14
5.3 Making Data Interoperable	14
5.4 Making Data Re-Usable	14
6. Allocation of Resources	15
7. Data security	16
8. Ethics	16
References	17

Figures

Figure 1 – example of the Action Log file for WP1 (as it is at 27/04/2023)	13
--	----

Tables

Table 1 – OVERWATCH Consortium	6
Table 2 – WP1 data mandatory information	8
Table 3 – WP2-3-4 data mandatory information	10
Table 4 – WP2-3-4 data optional information	11
Table 5 – WP5 data mandatory information	12
Table 6 – WP6 data mandatory information	13

Document revision history

Version	Date	Modification reason	Modified by
1	03/04/2023	First issue	Vanina Fissore, Luciana Dequal, Gianmarco Pignocchino, Federico Monteforte.
1.1	31/05/2023	Second issue	Vanina Fissore, Luciana Dequal, Federico Monteforte.

List of authors, contributors and reviewers

No.	Name	Role	Organisation
1	Vanina Fissore	Author	ITHACA
2	Luciana Dequal	Co-author	ITHACA
3	Gianmarco Pignocchino	Co-author	ITHACA
4	Federico Monteforte	Co-author	ITHACA
5	Elizabeth A. Nerantzis	Reviewer	ALPHA

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Management Services
CH	Chapter
D	Deliverable
DM	Data Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan
EGNSS	European Global Navigation Satellite System
EO	Earth Observation
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-Usable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The present deliverable is the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the OVERWATCH project. It is a short, general, and inclusive outline of the project policy for data management - i.e., collecting and sharing procedures - which includes an initial description of the datasets identified at the actual stage of the project that will be collected, processed or generated in all work packages during the 36 months of the OVERWATCH project. It contains all guidelines agreed by partners to allow data to be FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-Usable. The document can be also considered as a list of data to be adopted during the project lifetime.

The deliverable has been prepared with the collaborative work among the Coordinator and the Consortium Partners involved in data collection, production, and processing.

The deliverable is submitted six months after project start as required by the European Commission (EC) and foreseen by the Description of Action [RD04]. This Deliverable is expected to be periodically updated during the project lifetime, with new releases in M24 and M36 or anytime it is deemed necessary.

1. Introduction to OVERWATCH project

OVERWATCH aims to create a more intuitive, decentralised, informed, and precise system for several types of disasters, deployable in several phases of the disaster. The developed system will ensure a safer, more resilient, and capable response infrastructure, carrying out the crisis operation more cohesively. Leveraging on the state-of-the-art approach, OVERWATCH will design and develop a backend management platform that will cover the whole lifecycle of data management going from the data ingestion, harmonization, standardization, and data processing into exploitable information. Being supported by EGNSS (European Global Navigation Satellite System) and CEMS (Copernicus Emergency Management Services), the project aims to develop an Integrated holographic crisis management map to improve communication, information gathering, and coordination among disaster response teams. The system will be validated through two demonstrations in different countries. Extensive use of state-of-art Artificial intelligence techniques will guarantee to extrapolate valuable information coupling the variety of EO (Earth Observation) data with data collected from other sources (e.g. drones). This data will be stored in a dedicated Geospatial repository within the Management backend platform, which will be directly linked with an AR (Augmented Reality) user interaction/display module, providing the users with an immersive and dynamic overview of the event.

2. OVERWACTH Consortium

The OVERWATCH project consortium is composed by 10 partners from five different countries (Italy, Portugal, Poland, Germany, Denmark), consisting in the following members:

Beneficiary no.	Acronym	Designation	Country
1	ITH	ITHACA S.R.L.	IT
1.1	LINKS	FONDAZIONE LINKS - LEADING INNOVATION & KNOWLEDGE FOR SOCIETY	IT
2	ISQ	INSTITUTO DE SOLDADURA E QUALIDADE	PT
3	CBK	CENTRUM BADAN KOSMICZNYCH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
4	ENG	ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA SPA	IT
5	ROBOTTO	ROBOTTO CO APS	DK
6	INESCTEC	INESC TEC - INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIADE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES, TECNOLOGIA E CIENCIA	PT
7	HOLO	HOLO-INDUSTRIE 4.0 SOFTWARE GMBH	GE
8	CINAMIL	EXERCITO PORTUGUES	PT
9	ALPHA	ALPHA CONSULTANTS S.R.L.	IT

Table 1 – OVERWATCH Consortium

3. Aims of the Deliverable

The present Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines how the data are handled throughout the lifecycle of the OVERWATCH project in all the work packages, from their collection/generation up to their storage and archive.

The DMP defines the data management methodology in compliance with the FAIR data principles, i.e., in order to assure that the research data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Moreover, the DMP identifies the way the data will be stored and preserved along the project lifetime. This deliverable can also be considered as a list of data to be adopted within the 36 months of the project, and, consequently, as a living document that is expected to be updated and adjusted regularly, in line with the progress of the project. The first initial version (due in Month 6) will consequently evolve depending on significant changes arising and periodic reviews at relevant reporting stages of the project. Any changes during the last stage of the project will be reported in the last version of the Document.

All partners will be involved in the updating of the DMP, in accordance to the Grant Agreement (GA) [RD04] and Consortium Agreement (CA) [RD05], and will be supervised by the Data Manager (DM), Mr. Monteforte Federico (federico.monteforte@ithacaweb.org), appointed by ITHACA. The DM will coordinate the data management of the Project to assure usability, accountability and quality of the data and valorise them.

Also, as per GA, the DM will be supported by the Ethics and Security Manager and the Security, privacy and ethics internal committee, which will have as objectives to oversee that all activities gathering, processing and analysing sensitive data, ensure that the established procedures are followed and fulfil all obligations with regard to confidentiality while ensuring the compliance with the regulation including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The DMP has been prepared considering the template provided by the official Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Guidelines, and adapted based on the specificity of the project. The following structure has been accordingly defined:

- OVERWATCH Data Summary
- Description of FAIR data characteristics
- Allocation of resources
- Data Security
- Ethics

4. OVERWATCH Data Summary

All OVERWATCH datasets are reported in the current chapter. In order to provide a clear picture of the data, these are summarized and presented considering all six Work Packages (WPs), where WP2-WP3-WP4 have been grouped as they are the technical WPs. A brief description of each WP at the beginning of each section is included to correctly focus the theme and related data.

Moreover, the different types of data produced by the project can be grouped across the following identified categories:

- Documentation material: transcripts and agendas of meetings, recordings of meetings, videos and photos, reports.
- EO / EO-derived data: i.e. satellite data, raster and vector data, open datasets, etc..
- Drone images and videos.

- Location data: GNSS, others.

The tables have been organized as follows. For each row we have the following mandatory information:

- Dataset Name: the name of the dataset
- Data Type: see previous categorization
- Original Data Format: e.g. Jpeg, TIFF, pdf
- Data Provider: e.g. Copernicus, CERN, etc.
- Data source: e.g. Sentinel-1 • Data Access rights: only for internal usage, public, etc.
- Data access right: public or internal

Whenever available, or applicable, the following optional information are collected:

- Spatial resolution
- Temporal resolution
- Temporal coverage available
- Data Availability
- Metadata Available

4.1. WP 1

WP1 is dedicated to the collection of end-user requirements, functional and technical requirements of the OVERWATCH system. Consequently, the data of this WP are mainly documentation materials, i.e., information collected via interviews, workshops and other stakeholder engagement activities for transcription and further analysis.

DATA SET NAME	DATA TYPE	DATA FORMAT	DATA PROVIDER	DATA SOURCE	DATA ACCESS RIGHT
Notes and transcripts produced from workshops and other on-line meetings in document and audio file formats	notes	.docx	OVERWATCH	own	Internal
Recordings from workshops and other on-line in video file formats	video	.mp4	OVERWATCH	own	Internal

Table 2 – WP1 data mandatory information

4.2. WP 2 – Wp3 – WP 4

These WPs are devoted to the definition of the system architecture, to the development of the technological modules that will constitute the OVERWATCH system as a whole, (i.e., EO mapping, Drone mapping, AR Holographic interface, Fallback communication network), and to their final integration.

Table 3 provides the list of data and related mandatory information, while Table 4 reports related optional information, when available. In yellow colour, data related to the category of Drone images

and videos are shown; in green colour, the data of the EO / EO-derived data category and, finally in orange colour the data falling in the Location data category.

ID.	DATA SET NAME	DATA TYPE	ORIGINAL DATA FORMAT	DATA PROVIDER	DATA SOURCE	DATA ACCESS RIGHT
1	T.DRONE_I	IMAGES	*.jpg	INESCTEC	DRONE	PUBLIC
2	T.DRONE_V	VIDEO	*.MP4	INESCTEC	DRONE	PUBLIC
3	VTOL.DRONE_I	IMAGES	*.JPG	Robotto	DRONE	Internal
4	VTOL.DRONE_V	VIDEO	*.MP4	Robotto	DRONE	Internal
5	VTOL.DRONE_Ortho	raster	n/a	Robotto	Drone onboard	Internal
6	Drone images	IMAGES	*.jpg	Demo participants	DRONE	Internal
7	Drone videos	VIDEO	*.MP4	Demo participants	DRONE	Internal
8	LINKS-outputs (hazard maps)	raster	*.tif	LINKS	EO mapping service	PUBLIC
9	CBK-Floods (water extent)	raster	*.tif	CBK PAN	satellite	PUBLIC
10	DEM	raster	*.asc / *.tif / .xyz	(Polish) Head Office of Land Surveying and Cartography (GUGiK)	airborne LiDAR	PUBLIC
11	Sentinel-1	raster	*.tif	Copernicus	satellite	PUBLIC
12	Sentinel-2	raster	*.tif	Copernicus	satellite	PUBLIC
13	Other EO satellites	raster	*.tif	Various providers	satellite	PUBLIC
14	Ready-to-use open EO Imagery datasets	raster	*.tiff	Copernicus, Planet, Maxar	various (web platforms)	PUBLIC
15	Global Flood Monitoring (water extent)	raster / vector	*.tif / *.shp	Copernicus	satellite	PUBLIC

16	flood risk and hazard maps (ISOK)	raster / vector	WMS / *.shp	The State Water Holding Polish Waters	various, e.g. airborne LiDAR, GIS data	PUBLIC
17	LINKS-outputs (impacts)	vector	*.geojson	LINKS	EO mapping service	PUBLIC
18	topographic database BDOT10k	vector	*.shp / *.gml	(Polish) Head Office of Land Surveying and Cartography (GUGiK)	various (national database)	PUBLIC
19	OpenStreetMap	Vector	*.shp	OSM	various GIS data	PUBLIC
20	administrative boundaries	vector	*.shp	(Polish) Head Office of Land Surveying and Cartography (GUGiK)	land surveying (national database)	PUBLIC
21	LINKS-outputs (PVT data)	NMEA	*.ascii	LINKS	GNSS Receiver	PUBLIC

Table 3 – WP2-3-4 data mandatory information

ID.	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Temporal coverage available	Data availability	Metadata available
1 -7	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
8	>=10 m	<= 6 days (2 satellites)	from 2014 (S1), 2016 (S2)	open	yes
9	approx. 18 x 29 m (depending on latitude)	<= 6 days (2 satellites)	from 2023	open	yes
10	map scale 1:10 000	updated every few years	depends on region, not older than 2019	open	yes
11	10 m / 20 m / 60 m	< =5 days (2 satellites)	from 2016	open	yes
12	0.3 - 30 m	various	various	open / paid	yes
13	>=15cm	>=1 day	various	On demand	yes
14	>= 0.3m	various	various	open	yes

15	map scale 1:10 000	"static"	current (now for 2022)	open (as WMS); SHP on request	no
16	1 m	updated every few years	depends on region, not older than 2019	open	no
17	>=10 m	<= 6 days (2 satellites)	from 2016 (Sentinel 2)	open	yes
18	map scale 1:5000 or smaller	constantly updated	constantly updated	open	no
19	map scale 1:10 000	updated on a regular basis	current	open	no
20	approx. 20 m	<= 6 days (2 satellites)	from 2014	open	yes
21	n/a	1 second	n/a	open	no

Table 4 – WP2-3-4 data optional information

4.3. WP 5

WP5 is dedicated to the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities, and consequently it delivers and produces standard dissemination and communication materials. Also, information collected via interviews, workshops and other stakeholder engagement activities will serve as inputs for the exploitation activity.

DATA SET NAME	DATA TYPE	DATA FORMAT	DATA PROVIDER	DATA SOURCE	DATA ACCESS RIGHT
Newsletter contact	table	.xsl	ALPHA	various	Internal
Personal information (BP interviews)	table	.xls	ALPHA	various	Internal
Visual content	images, videos	*.jpg, *.mp4	ALPHA	various (websites)	Public
Project graphic kit	Logo, ppt, graphics	*.ppt, *.jpg, *.png	ALPHA	various (websites, graphic tools)	Public
Promotional material	Brochure, newsletter	*.doc, pdf	ALPHA	various (graphic tools)	Public
Market analysis data to identify market segmentation and trends	Unstructured	*.doc, pdf	ALPHA	Fragmented. Source will be presented in related deliverables.	Internal

Competitive environment assessment data to map main competing solutions and main stakeholders	Unstructured	*.doc, pdf	ALPHA	Fragmented. Source will be presented in related deliverables.	Internal
Data to draft SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats) and barriers to entry for OVERWATCH	Unstructured	*.doc, pdf	ALPHA	Fragmented. Source will be presented in related deliverables.	Internal
Data for Preliminary business model(s) definition	Unstructured	*.doc, pdf	ALPHA + Consortium	Fragmented. Source will be presented in related deliverables.	Internal
Data for Pricing strategy (considering potential users' desired data and constrains)	Unstructured	*.doc, pdf	ALPHA	Fragmented. Source will be presented in related deliverables.	Internal
Overall Business Plan definition quantifying key assumptions (incl. pricing, market share, CAPEX, OPEX...), over a 5 to 10 years period, to obtain a long-term cash-flow prediction	Unstructured	*.doc, pdf	ALPHA + Consortium	ALPHA know-how based on Consortium partner contributions	Internal
Risk analysis data and information in relation to OVERWATCH uptake and identify main actions to avoid/mitigate	Unstructured	*.doc, pdf	ALPHA + Consortium	ALPHA know-how based on Consortium partner contributions	Internal
Implementation roadmap: key strategies and drivers for the exploitation activities and solution adoption (from both a consortium and individual point of view).	Unstructured	*.doc, pdf	ALPHA + Consortium	ALPHA know-how based on Consortium partner contributions	Internal

Table 5 – WP5 data mandatory information

4.4. WP 6

This WP is dedicated to project's coordination and it will mainly collect documentation materials such as meeting minutes, reports, recordings, and a document (excel file – “Action Log”, see Figure 1) dedicated to the progress monitoring for each WP, where all fundamental actions are indicated, monitored and updated by the WP/task leader in charge of the specific actions.

DATA SET NAME	DATA TYPE	DATA FORMAT	DATA PROVIDER	DATA SOURCE	DATA ACCESS RIGHT
Recording of meetings	multimedia	*.mp4	ITHACA	Microsoft Teams	internal use
Minutes of meetings	documents	*.doc	ITHACA	n/a	internal use
Agendas of meeting	documents	*.doc	ITHACA	n/a	open
Action log	documents	*.xlsm	ITHACA	Microsoft Teams	internal use

Table 6 – WP6 data mandatory information

Action Log	
OVERWATCH - WP1	
Last status update: 27/04/2023	
Status	#
Open	0
In Progress	1
Done	14
Cancelled	0
Sum	15

No.	Task	Action Log description	Responsible	Support	Deadline	Status
1	WP1	Manage settings in WP1 weekly call // lack of chat functionality is a case when you log in via a link, that is then being opened in your default browser that has other TEAMS account logged in. In case of running two logged in TEAM accounts in the same time, please copy link to another browser / open private tab / join directly from TEAMS app	Emil Wrzosek	all	09/12/22	Done
2	T1.1	Fill the EUB and AB tables	José Borges	all	09/12/22	Done
3	T1.1	Provide (min) 5 references/partner for the SoTA table	José Borges	all	07/12/22	Done
4	T1.1	Provide comments on the methodology for capturing Use Cases and End-user requirements	José Borges	all	07/12/22	Done
5	T1.1	Provide feedback on benefits and tasks for the OVERWATCH's Advisory and End-user boards	José Borges	all	09/12/22	Done
6	T1.1	Provide a draft version of presentation for mid-Jan Workshops	José Borges	all	16/12/22	Done
7	T1.3	Establish a date for bi-weekly T1.3 meeting	Claudio Rossi		27/01/23	Done
8	T1.3	Discuss and freeze the microservice architecture pattern	Claudio Rossi	all	February 23	Done
9	T1.3	Further detailing each architecture block	Claudio Rossi	all	February 23	Done
10	T1.1	Contribute to D1.1 (draft)	José Borges	all	23/02/23	Done
11	T1.1	Contribute to D1.1	José Borges	all	03/03/23	Done
12	T1.1	Set a date and invite participants for AB meeting	José Borges	Emil Wrzosek	24/02/23	Done
13	T1.1	D1.1 Ready for final revision + proofreading	José Borges	Emil Wrzosek	21/03/23	Done
14	T1.1	Delivery of D1.1	José Borges	Emil Wrzosek	31/03/23	Done
15	T1.3	D1.3 ToC drafted and shared	Giuseppe Veilla		07/04/23	In Progress

Figure 1 – example of the Action Log file for WP1 (as of 27/04/2023)

5. FAIR Data

This section of the DMP presents the adopted measures to ensure that the data of the OVERWATCH project comply with the FAIR data principles of **Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Re-usability**.

The FAIR principles articulate the attributes data need to have to enable and enhance reuse, by humans and machines. It has long been recognized that it is not sufficient simply to post data and other research-related materials onto the web and hope that the motivation and skill of the potential user would be sufficient to enable reuse. There is a need for various things, including contextual and supporting information (metadata), to allow those data to be discovered, understood, and used.

According to the FAIR data principles, scientific data should be managed in order to be easily accessed and exchanged, promoting knowledge and innovation. In practice, the following general indications will be followed to assure the FAIR data principles:

Findability – clear naming of data and metadata, use of search keywords, and unique identifier that will optimize the potential of finding and re-using the data.

Accessibility – details on the repository in which the data will be made available and what tools are needed to access the data.

Interoperability – use of vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies that will be used to enable data exchange, re-use and interoperability.

Re-usability – information on when and for which duration data are made available, and on licensing of data.

5.1 Making Data Findable

Data and research outputs findability will be ensured by adopting a generally recognized naming convention for data and for metadata. Moreover, findability will be assured by two components:

- 1) a unique identifier (e.g. Digital Object Identifier - DOI) for data and metadata;
- 2) an easily accessible service to locate the data resource over time ensuring uniqueness in location.

Given such premises, the project fulfils the requirements to adopt an OpenAIR compliant repository such as Zenodo [RD01] ensuring to be compliant with all European directives. Zenodo is a free of charge, open data repository created by OpenAIRE and CERN and is financed by the EU.

5.2 Making Data Accessible

OVERWATCH will support the continuous effort to benefit for society by contributing to a global open science approach with the objective of transforming the scientific culture towards a more open, accessible, multidisciplinary, collaborative scientific community. OVERWATCH will comply with the open science policy of Horizon Europe as detailed in the Programme Regulation (Art. 14 and 39(3)) and further described in the General Model Grant Agreement (Art. 17 – Specific Rules).

In order to guarantee data accessibility, all the data and research outputs generated during the project lifetime, after proper referencing, will be published in the Zenodo open data repository. The adoption of Zenodo ensures to be compliant with all European directives devoted to guarantee the Open Access to research data outputs, i.e., ensuring accessibility to general public and interested entities (scientists, stakeholders, policy makers). The service offered by Zenodo can handle any file format of size up to 50GB, enabling the sharing of results and also promoting data re-use. Using Zenodo will increase the discoverability of the gathered data that are being made publicly available by OVERWATCH. Also, public documents (e.g. deliverables) will be as well made available on the OVERWATCH website. The documents will be available in protected PDF files.

5.3 Making Data Interoperable

Interoperability and interconnection of generated data during the project lifecycle will be ensured through the adoption of conventional accepted formats and standards for all data generated within the OVERWATCH project. OVERWATCH will adopt the Metadata Standards Directory [RD02] and FAIRsharing [RD03] as references to ensure that each product/component developed along project lifetime will meet traditional quality and consistency standards while they remain interoperable with other data sources at the same time. FAIRsharing standards also include standards for Metadata and guidelines for data management, providing guidelines for the most used geodata formats (e.g. Shapefiles, geoJSON, CSV, NetCDF, etc.), which also enables the creation and the provision of map layers through OGC standards (e.g. WMTS, WMS).

5.4 Making Data Re-Usable

Project research outputs such as software, algorithms, protocols, workflows and others, as long as deemed not key information for the project exploitation, will be available for download and project outcomes review and validation enabling reusability.

OVERWATCH will make its data publicly available under the Creative Commons Licensing scheme, which is also supported by Zenodo. Specifically, the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial International 4.0, that: 1) enables the re-use of data, 2) ensures that the source and the authority of the data are recognized, and 3) protects the commercial interests of the participants, will be adopted as reference of the licensing scheme for making the data available.

6. Allocation of Resources

The Data Management Plan is a living document, and it will be updated regularly by the lead beneficiary and reviewed by WP-leads and the Coordinator with the purpose of supporting the data management lifecycle for all data that will be collected, processed and/or generated by the project. Before updating the DMP, the Coordinator shall be notified, and the final update shall be approved by them.

The responsibilities of the lead beneficiary are to update the DMP as a deliverable when significant changes arise, and – together with the DM – assist the consortium partners with specific questions in relation to the DMP.

The Coordinator is responsible for ensuring proper management and processing of all data in the project, complying with the EU data protection regulations. Moreover, the Coordinator oversees uploading the deliverables to the Participant Portal and to place a copy on Microsoft SharePoint repository, adopted for the project, as agreed by the partners. The data shared among consortium partners, necessary for project implementation activities, are uploaded and stored in the adopted Microsoft SharePoint.

The public deliverables will also be uploaded by the Coordination team to the Zenodo Platform, including the datasets related to the documents, at the same time they are made available on the Participant Portal. Other types of public data also must be uploaded to Zenodo by the coordination team.

The responsibilities of the project members include:

- Regular update and classification of the data collected and generated in OVERWATCH
- Implementing and respecting the Data Management Plan.
- Before the start of any task that requires processing of any kind of personal data, an analysis of the types of personal data necessary will be made with the participation of the respective partners, who will also request the opinions of the DM with the support of the Ethics Security Manager.

Moreover, costs related to open-access to research data in Horizon Europe are eligible for reimbursement under the conditions defined in the Grant Agreement. Project beneficiaries will be responsible for applying for reimbursement for costs related to making data accessible to others beyond the consortium.

The costs for making data FAIR includes:

- Fees associated with the publication of scientific articles containing project's research data in "Gold" Open access journals. The cost sharing, in case of multiple authors, shall be decided among the authors on a case-by-case basis.
- Data archiving at Zenodo and on other online data base: free of charge
- Copyright licensing with Creative Commons: free of charge
- OVERWATCH website operations: ad hoc budget foreseen

Each partner is responsible for the data they produce. Any fee incurred for Open Access through scientific publication of the data will be the responsibility of the data owner (authors) partner(s).

7. Data security

In compliance with the EU 2016/679, also known as General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Directive 2009/136/EC and in line with the OVERWATCH Grant Agreement art. 15.2, the OVERWATCH consortium will provide a safe and accessible environment for data storage, ensuring that data is preserved for future use. To this end, the internal SharePoint of the project Coordinator (ITHACA) will be adopted and *ad-hoc* configured in order to be compliant with the GDPR. More detailed information can be derived from the following internet page: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/compliance/regulatory/gdpr>. For this purpose, various measures will be implemented to ensure data security, including:

1. Data encryption to prevent unauthorized access;
2. Restricted access control of sensitive data based on roles and responsibilities;
3. Regular backups of data and drafting of recovery plan in the event of a system failure or data breach;
4. Secure transfer protocols for sensitive data (e.g. SFTP);
5. Trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation of data with established policies and procedures for data quality control, archiving, and access control;
6. Well-organized folder structure and systematic file labelling to ensure final data set consistency.

8. Ethics

OVERWATCH is fully aware that the project's activities may generate ethical, fundamental rights, privacy and data protection implications and is fully committed to adhere to the highest standards at the European and International level. All researchers in the project, at all levels (Principal Investigator, researchers, technicians, etc.), will commit to adhere to the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity \[RD06\]](#) and to uphold the highest ethical standards throughout the project, through forms circulated by the project coordinator.

Moreover, all project partners are obliged by European and national law (e.g., GDPR) to protect personal data. The OVERWATCH Coordinator ensures that the privacy and confidentiality of partner data is protected during data sharing and long-term retention. To this end, anonymized data and appropriate technical and organizational measures will be implemented to safeguard the data.

Additionally, the ethical and legal implications of data sharing will be carefully considered, ensuring that partners are properly recognized and accredited for their contributions, protecting against intellectual property rights infringements, and ensuring that data sharing is consistent with data protection and privacy laws.

All project partners are expected to act in accordance with ethical guidelines and principles and promptly report any ethical concerns or violations to the project coordinator. In the event of ethical violations, the project coordinator has a duty to take appropriate action to address the issue and ensure that the project continues to comply with ethical aspects. Failure to comply with ethical guidelines and principles may result in termination of the partnership or other appropriate sanctions.

Ethical issues related to DMP will be implemented in close synergy with Ethics deliverable of WP6, namely "D. 6.3 – Privacy, Ethics and security report" due on M12, and then updated at M36.

References

ID	Title	Access Date
[RD01]	Zenodo OpenData Repository. Link .	2023
[RD02]	RDA Metadata Standards Directory .Link .	2023
[RD03]	FAIRsharing.org Standards, databases, policies. Link	2023
[RD04]	OVERWATCH Grant agreement No. 101082320	2023
[RD05]	OVERWATCH Consortium Agreement	2023
[RD06]	European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity	2023